

Attitude of Nursing Students Towards Artificial Intelligence (AI) at a Public Sector Institute. A Descriptive Analysis

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to advanced technological systems designed to mimic human intelligence, enabling machines to perform tasks such as decision-making, problem-solving, and learning. **Objective:** The objective of this study is to determine the attitudes of nursing students towards the use of artificial intelligence in nursing education and practice. **Methods:** Cross sectional study was conducted at Public Sector College of nursing of Karachi among 136 undergraduate nursing students. Sample size was calculated by using OpenEpi software. Convenient sampling technique was used to gather the data. An open access validated and reliable tool was used, named artificial intelligence attitude scale. Data was analyzed by using SPSS version 27.0. **Results:** A total of 150 participants were included in the study. Most were aged ≤ 25 years (96.0%). The majority agreed or strongly agreed that AI is an important advancement (89.3%) and makes life easier (90.6%). Overall, participants demonstrated a generally positive attitude toward artificial intelligence. **Conclusion:** The study findings indicate that nursing students demonstrated a moderate to high attitude towards AI, recognizing its benefits and usefulness while also expressing concerns related to risk, reduced human interaction, and job replacement

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Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to advanced technological systems designed to mimic human intelligence, enabling machines to perform tasks such as decision-making, problem-solving, and learning. In the healthcare context, AI is increasingly being used to enhance patient care, improve efficiency, and support clinical decision-

making (1). AI is the process by which a computer or machine learns by simulating a lot of data. AI is widely employed in many different sectors and technology (2). The information technologies should be included in year one modules, as per the WHO European Strategy for Nursing and Midwifery Education, we hypothesized that the results would allow us to envision appropriate curriculum changes (3). Since it affects how they will interact with AI technologies in the future and incorporate them into healthcare procedures, it is essential to comprehend nursing students' perspectives towards AI (4). It is becoming more and more important for nurse education programs to equip student nurses with the skills and willingness to use AI technology in their nursing practice as it develops (5). Additionally, healthcare is using AI-predictive analytics to identify patients who are more likely to experience difficulties, allowing for more individualized treatment and prompt interventions (6). AI has been widely incorporated into decision support systems (DSSs) (7). AI technology has advanced quickly, and its application in nursing education and healthcare is growing (8). Only 3.8% of nursing students received AI-related instruction during their undergraduate studies, and 70% of nurses in the US, a leader in cutting-edge health technology, were ignorant about AI-based healthcare solutions (9). It is essential to comprehend these elements in order to develop AI-focused curricula that support nursing students in developing favorable attitudes about the deployment of AI (10). National and international AI ethical norms are the result of growing understanding of AI ethics. Assessing nursing students' AI ethics then makes it possible to determine their educational needs and include pertinent material to the nursing curriculum (11). Improving student nurses' understanding of AI may result in a more effective application of this technology in the medical field (12). The objective of this study is to determine the attitudes of nursing students towards the use of artificial intelligence in nursing education and practice.

METHODS

The descriptive, Cross sectional study conducted at a public sector college of Nursing, Karachi. The population was student of Generic BS Nursing. Non probability sample technique was used. A sample size of 136 from a population of 200 achieves 80.65% power to detect a difference (P1-P0) of 0.05 using a two-sided exact test with a significance level (alpha) of 0.05. Students who are already using advanced AI training programs or have formal training in AI-based learning systems and willing to participate was included in the study. Those students who are not appear in institute during data collection. An open access, validated and reliable tool was used to conduct the study named artificial intelligence attitude scale, (13). A reliability analysis was performed on the scale comprising 13 items and three factors. Cronbach's alpha analysis was used to figure out how reliable both the overall scale and the sub-dimensions were in this case. The overall scale's Cronbach's alpha reliability value was .802. Furthermore, the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients for the sub-dimensions of the scale varied between .679 and .781(14). Approval for the study was obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of Qatar College of Nursing (Female), Karachi. Permission for data collection was also be taken from the concerned department of the same institution. To ensure privacy, no personal names was recorded; instead, number codes was used for participants. They were allowed to withdraw from the study without any penalty.

RESULTS

Table 1 describes the demographic characteristics of the study participants most of the participants (96.0) were ≤ 25 years of age and unmarried, first years students constituted largest academic group (32.7). The majority belonged to nuclear family (61.3).

Table-1: Demographic Characteristics of the Participants (n = 150)

Characteristics	n (%)
Age	
Up To 25 Years	144 (96.0)
More Than 25 Years	6 (4.0)
Academic Year	
First Year	49 (32.7)
Second Year	35 (23.3)
Third Year	33 (22.0)
Forth Year	33 (22.0)
Marital Status	
Single	141 (94.0)
Married	9 (6.0)
Family Status	
Nuclear Family	92 (61.3)
Joint Family	40 (26.7)
Single Parent Family	18 (12.0)

Table 2 presents participants response to AIAS statements. Most participants agreed that AI is beneficial and useful. Concerns regarding reduced communication and job replacement were common. Neutral response were 75.3%observed for threat and creativity related statements.

Table-2: Participants Responses to AIAS Statements

S.#	Statement	Strongly Disagree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	Neutral n (%)	Agree n (%)	Strongly Agree n (%)
1	I think artificial intelligence is an important advancement.	2 (1.3)	1 (0.7)	13 (8.7)	80 (53.3)	54 (36.0)
2	I believe artificial intelligence makes life easier for people.	4(2.7)	3(2.0)	7(4.7)	77(51.3)	59(39.3)
3	I believe artificial intelligence will provide significant contributions to humanity.	4(2.7)	11(7.3)	43(28.7)	72(48.0)	20(13.3)
4	I see artificial intelligence as a threat.	8(5.3)	30(20.0)	50(33.3)	50(33.3)	12(8.0)
5	I think artificial intelligence reduces human-to-human communication.	3(2.5)	15(10.0)	19(12.7)	56(37.3)	57(38.0)
6	I am concerned that artificial intelligence will replace human labor.	4(2.7)	13(8.7)	26(17.3)	79(52.7)	28(18.7)
7	I believe artificial intelligence destroys creativity.	3(2.0)	9(6.0)	32(21.3)	62(41.3)	44(29.3)
8	I enjoy using artificial intelligence to produce textual content.	2(1.3)	16(10.7)	42(28.0)	78(52.0)	11(7.3)

9	I like keeping up with developments in artificial intelligence.	1(0.7)	13(8.7)	47(31.3)	71(47.3)	18(12.0)
10	I enjoy talking about topics related to artificial intelligence.	4(2.7)	19(12.7)	44(29.3)	60(40.0)	23(15.3)
11	I would like to chat with artificial intelligence.	10(6.7)	33(22.0)	38(25.3)	47(31.3)	21(14.0)
12	I enjoy creating visual products using artificial intelligence.	7(4.7)	32(21.3)	35(23.3)	62(41.3)	14(9.3)
13	I would like to use artificial intelligence tools for entertainment purposes	13(8.7)	33(22.0)	40(26.7)	50(33.3)	14(9.3)

Table 3 displays the median ASAI total and sub scores. Overall attitude towards AI was 48.0 (IQR: 44.0–51.0) moderate to high. The highest median score was observed for the “Using AI “components. And risk was 12.0, 15.0, and 20.5 respectively. Scores ranges variability indicates in perception among participants.

Table-3: ASAI Scores of the Participants

Component	Median (IQR)	Min-Max
Benefits	12 (11.00-13.25)	3-15
Risk	15 (13.00-17.00)	7-20
Using AI	20.50 (17.00-24.00)	10-59
Total	48.0 (44.0-51.0)	23-92

Table 4 compares ASAI scores across demographic variables. A statically significant difference was observed by family status (p- 0.004).Participants from nuclear family had higher median scores. No significant difference were found for age, academic years and marital status.

Table-4: Comparison of ASAI Scores by Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Characteristics	Median (IQR)	p-value
Age		0.096 ^a
Up To 25 Years	48.0 (44.0-51.0)	
More Than 25 Years	39.50(29.0-51.75)	
Academic Year		0.088 [‡]
First Year	49.0(44.50-53.0)	
Second Year	48.0(44.0-54.0)	
Third Year	48.0(42.0-50.0)	
Forth Year	45.0(42.0-49.50)	
Marital Status		0.444 [~]
Single	48.0(44.0-51.0)	
Married	46.0(36.50-51.0)	
Family Status		0.004^{‡*}

Nuclear Family	49.0(44.0-53.0)
Joint Family	46.0(42.0-50.0)
Single Parent Family	45.50(40.70-48.0)

~ Mann-Whitney U Test

‡ Kruskal-Wallis H Test

* Significant at 5% Level of Significance

DISCUSSION

The level of attitude of regarding uses of AI were assessed among 150 nursing students. According to the demographic most of them (96%) were aged ≤ 25 years. The majority were single (94%), with first-year students forming the largest group (32.7%). Most participants (61.3%) belonged to nuclear families (15). The results of this study showed that most nursing students have a positive attitude toward (AI). Around 89% of students agreed that AI is an important development, and about 90% believed that it makes life easier. This shows that students are generally open to using AI in nursing practice. Another study has been conducted in Palestine in 2025, showed a positive attitude toward the benefits of AI, especially for beneficial applications of AI and being impressed by AI capabilities, but reported low positivity for AI creating new professional opportunities (16). Although students also showed strong awareness of AI risks and dangers ($p < .001$) (17). However many students also had concerns about AI. Nearly 47.5% were worried about data privacy, 25.3% about hacking, and many felt that AI could reduce human–patient interaction. About 71% believed that AI might replace human jobs, showing fear about the future role of nurses. Another study conducted by El Arab, in 2025 reported that nurses showed moderate concern about AI safety and errors, but younger nurses are more optimistic. Whereas key factors shaping AI attitudes and uses include perceived usefulness, ease of use, self-efficacy, digital literacy, and organizational support (18, 19). Most students had no previous AI experience (64.3%), and more than half learned about AI from social media (53.2%), while only 16.6% learned through university. This may explain why students felt less confident about the practical use of AI, even though they were willing to use it. In contrast, a study conducted in Pakistan in 2025 reported most students had good knowledge of AI (93.3%) and prior experience with AI tools (83.3%) (20).

CONCLUSION

The study findings indicate that nursing students demonstrated a moderate to high attitude towards AI, recognizing its benefits and usefulness while also expressing concerns related to risk, reduced human interaction, and job replacement. These results highlight the need for targeted educational strategies to address concerns and promote balanced, informed use of artificial intelligence in nursing education and practice.

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